

Studies in Furan Derivatives: Part IV.* Syntheses of some Bromo and Iodo Benzofuran Derivatives

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Bromination of methyl 5-hydroxy-3-methylcoumarilate and its methyl ether with bromine furnished mono, di and tribromo derivatives. Bromination of the methyl ether has also been studied with N-bromo-succinimide. Iodination of methyl 6-hydroxy-3-methyl-coumarilate furnished the 7-iodo derivative and that of its methylether furnished a mixture of 5-and 7-iodo derivative. Some bromo and iodo benzofurans of known orientations have also been synthesised from the corresponding bromo and iodo phenolic aldehydes and ketones.

The work on the bromination of benzofuran derivatives described in an earlier paper¹ has now been extended and some further studies have been made.

Methyl 5-hydroxy-3-methylcoumarilate (A) obtained from the known 5-methoxy-3-methylcoumarilic acid² gave with one mole of bromine in acetic acid a monobromo derivative which on hydrolysis gave a monobromo acid identical with the one previously prepared by Dalvi and Sethna² by a different method and to which the 4 (or 6) bromo-5-hydroxy-3-methylcoumarilic acid structure was assigned. The N.M R. spectrum (fig. 1) showed it to be the 4-bromo derivative. With four moles of bromine the ester (A) gave a dibromo derivative which did not react with alkali and hence was assigned the 4, 6-dibromo structure. This was confirmed by the NMR spectrum (fig. 2) of its methyl ether. The methyl ether of the dibromo derivative with N-bromosuccinimide gave a tribromo derivative, different from the 4,6,7-tribromo derivative described later and hence was assigned the methyl 3-bromomethyl 4,6-dibromo-5-methoxycoumarilate structure.

FIG 1

The methyl ether of (A) on bromination with one mole of bromine or with N-bromo-succinimide gave the 4-bromo derivative, identical with the methyl ether of the monobromo derivative described above. On hydrolysis it gave the corresponding acid, the decarboxylation of which resulted in an unworkable mass. With liquid bromine the methoxy ester

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1. V. Salvi and S. Sethna, *This Journal*, 1967, **44**, 135.

2. V. J. Dalvi and S. Sethna, *This Journal*, 1949, **26**, 468.

gave a tribromo derivative which remained unchanged on reaction with either morpholine or acetic anhydride and sodium acetate. Therefore there was no bromine in the side chain and the 4, 6, 7-tribromo structure has been assigned to this compound. This has been confirmed by the NMR data (fig. 2).

FIG. 2

NMR data: In order to confirm the structures of the mono, di and tribromo derivatives high resolution NMR studies were made on a Varian Spectrometer at 56.445 MC/S and the spectra are shown in figures 1 and 2 respectively. The spectra of the di and tri-bromo derivatives were studied in CDCl_3 whereas the mono bromo derivative was dissolved in acetone- d_6 for this purpose. The assignments of the various lines are also shown in the respective figures. The chemical shifts are reported relative to tetramethylsilane (TMS) as internal standard.

Figure 1 shows the presence of one CH_3 group, one COOCH_3 group and two phenyl protons. The quartet due to the two phenyl protons with a coupling constant of 9.9 c/s indicates that these two protons are present in the ortho position with respect to each other. Hence, the mono bromo derivative has been assigned the 4-bromo structure. From figure 2, it is clear that there is one CH_3 , one OCH_3 and one COOCH_3 group. This along with a line at 7.76 ppm with an intensity of one proton per molecule indicates that the dibromo derivative has the 4,6-dibromo structure. Figure 2 indicates the presence of one CH_3 , one COOCH_3 and one OCH_3 group in the tribromo derivative. The presence of CH_2Br grouping or any aromatic proton is not indicated and hence it is proved that all the three bromine atoms are substituted in the phenyl ring.

Methyl 6-hydroxy-3-methylcoumarilate¹ on iodination with equivalent quantities of iodine and iodic acid gave the 7-iodo derivative which on methylation and hydrolysis gave the known 7-iodo-6-methoxy-3-methylcoumarilic acid². This on decarboxylation gave 7-iodo-6-methoxy-3-methylbenzofuran which was also obtained when 2-acetyl-6-iodo-5-methoxy-phenol⁴ was condensed with ethyl bromoacetate and the phenoxy acetic ester obtained was hydrolysed to the corresponding acid and the latter simultaneously cyclised and decarboxylated. The hydroxy ester on iodination with four equivalent of iodine and iodic acid gave an unworkable product but its methyl ether on iodination with one equivalent of iodine and iodic acid or with excess gave a mixture of the known 7-iodo and the known 5-iodo derivative, previously prepared by Lele and Sethna³ from 3, 8 and 3, 6-di-iodo-7-methoxy-4-methylcoumarin.

7-Bromo-4-methoxy-3-methylbenzofuran and 5-iodo-4-methoxy-2-methylbenzofuran were synthesised from 2-hydroxy-3-bromo-6-methoxyacetophenone and 2-hydroxy-

5-iodo-6-methoxyacetophenone⁴ by condensation with ethyl bromoacetate, hydrolysis of the intermediate phenoxy ester to the acid and simultaneous cyclisation and decarboxylation by heating with acetic anhydride and fused sodium acetate. 5-Bromo-2-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzaldehyde on a similar series of reactions gave 5-bromo-7-methoxycoumarilic acid instead of the decarboxylated product. The same product was also obtained when the above aldehyde was condensed with ethyl bromomalonate and the intermediate oil obtained was hydrolysed.

EXPERIMENTAL*

Methyl 5-methoxy-3-methylcoumarilate: 5-Methoxy-3-methyl-coumarilic acid² (0.2 g.) and dimethyl sulphate (0.12 g.) were refluxed in acetone solution in presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate (0.4 g.) for 6 hr. Acetone was removed and the reaction mixture was added to water. The separated product crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 88-89°. (Found: C, 65.63; H, 5.40. $C_{12}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 65.44; H, 5.49%).

Methyl 5-hydroxy-3-methylcoumarilate: The above ester (1 g.) was mixed with anhydrous aluminium chloride (2 g.) and refluxed in dry benzene for 4 hr. on a steam bath. On cooling, dilute hydrochloric acid was added. The product which separated crystallised from xylene in needles (0.4 g.), m.p. 191°. (Found: C, 64.40; H, 4.61. $C_{11}H_{10}O_4$ requires C, 64.07; H, 4.89%).

Methyl 4-bromo-5-hydroxy-3-methylcoumarilate: The above hydroxy ester (1 g.) in acetic acid (10 ml.) was treated with bromine (0.8 g.) in acetic acid (8 ml.). The reaction mixture was kept at room temperature for 4 hr. The product which separated was crystallised from acetic acid in needles (0.8 g.), m.p. 179°. (Found: Br, 28.42. $C_{11}H_9O_4$ Br requires Br, 28.07%).

The above ester (1 g.) was heated with alcoholic sodium hydroxide solution (20 ml.; 10%) for 5 min. on a steam bath and then kept at room temperature for 4 hr. The product which separated on acidification crystallised from dilute alcohol and gave m.p. 238.40° (decomp). Mixed m.p. with the 4 (or 6) -bromo-5-hydroxy-3-methylcoumarilic acid of Dalvi and Sethna² was not depressed.

Methyl 4, 6-dibromo-5-hydroxy-3-methylcoumarilate: Methyl-5-hydroxy-3-methyl-coumarilate (1 g.) was dissolved in hot acetic acid (10 ml.) and the hot solution was treated with bromine (3.2 g.) in acetic acid (32 ml.). The reaction mixture was left overnight at room temperature. The product which separated crystallised from acetic acid in needles (0.8 g.), m.p. 169-70°. (Found: Br, 44.08. $C_{11}H_8O_4Br_2$ requires Br, 43.95%).

The methyl ether: Prepared by refluxing with dimethyl sulphate and potassium carbonate in acetone solution for 4 hr., and crystallised from acetic acid, gave m.p. 166°. (Found: C, 38.55; H, 2.99; Br, 42.31. $C_{12}H_{10}O_4Br_2$ requires C, 38.10; H, 2.65; Br, 42.33%).

Methyl 3-bromomethyl-4, 6-dibromo-5-methoxycoumarilate: The above methyl ether (1 g.) was refluxed with N-bromosuccinimide (1 g.) in chloroform (10 ml.) for 6 hr. on a steam

*All the m.p.s. are uncorrected.

4. M. V. Shah and S. Sethna, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 2676.

bath. The product obtained on removal of the solvent was crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 168°. (Found: Br, 52.28. $C_{12}H_9O_4Br_3$ requires Br, 52.52%).

Methyl 4-bromo-5-methoxy-3-methylcoumarilate: Methyl-5-methoxy-3-methylcoumarilate (1.1 g.) in acetic acid (10 ml.) was treated with bromine (0.8 g.) in acetic acid (8 ml.). The reaction mixture was kept at room temperature for 4 hr. and worked up as before. The product crystallised from acetic acid in needles (0.8 g.), m.p. 115°. (Found: Br, 26.55. $C_{12}H_{11}O_4Br$ requires Br, 26.75 %).

The same monobromo derivative was obtained when methyl 4-bromo-5-hydroxy-3-methylcoumarilate (2.8 g.) was refluxed with anhydrous potassium carbonate (5 g.) and dimethyl sulphate (1.2 g.) in acetone (50 ml.) for 6 hr., or when methyl 5-methoxy-3-methylcoumarilate (0.5 g.) in chloroform (5 ml.) was refluxed with N-bromosuccinimide (0.5 g.) for 6 hr.

4-Bromo-5-methoxy-3-methylcoumarilic acid: The above ester (1 g.) was hydrolysed by heating with alcoholic sodium hydroxide solution (20 ml.; 10%) for 1 hr. on a steam bath. The acid crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 295-96°. (Found: C, 46.22; H 2.98; Br, 27.74. $C_{11}H_9O_4Br$ requires C, 46.33; H, 3.16; Br, 28.07%).

Methyl 4, 6, 7-tribromo-5-methoxy-3-methylcoumarilate: Methyl-5-methoxy-3-methylcoumarilate (0.5 g.) was treated with liquid bromine (1ml.) and kept overnight. The reaction mixture was treated with sodium bisulphite to remove excess of bromine, and then with sodium hydroxide solution to remove demethylated product, if any. The product was crystallised from acetic acid in needles (0.5 g.), m.p. 226-28°. (Found: Br, 52.31. $C_{12}H_9O_4Br_3$ requires Br, 52.52%).

Methyl 7-iodo-6-hydroxy-3-methylcoumarilate: Methyl-6-hydroxy-3-methylcoumarilate (1 g.) in alcohol (10 ml.) was treated with iodine (0.4 g.) and iodic acid (0.2 g.). The reaction mixture was stirred for 1 hr. The separated product was crystallised from alcohol in needles (0.8 g.), m.p. 190°. (Found: I, 38.25. $C_{11}H_9O_4I$ requires I, 38.26%).

The methyl ether, prepared as before, was crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 180°. Mixed m.p. with an authentic specimen of methyl 7-iodo-6-methoxy-3-methylcoumarilate³ was not depressed.

The above ester (1. g.) when heated with alcoholic sodium hydroxide solution (10 ml.; 10%) for 2 hr. on a steam bath gave the known 7-iodo-6-methoxy-3-methylcoumarilic acid³, m.p. 222° (effler).

7-Iodo-6-methoxy-3-methylbenzofuran: The above acid (0.5 g.) was refluxed with copper (0.1 g.) and quinoline (2 ml.) for 40 minutes. The product which separated on working up as usual crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 99°. (Found: C, 41.22, H, 2.92; I, 44.19. $C_{11}H_9O_2I$ requires C, 41.68; H, 3.13; I, 44.10%).

Ethyl-2-acetyl-6-iodo-5-methoxyphenoxyacetate: 2-Hydroxy-3-iodo-4-methoxyacetophenone (0.97 g.) was dissolved in acetone (30 ml.) and refluxed with ethyl bromoacetate (0.55 g.) in the presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate (2 g.) on a steam bath for 6 hr. The product obtained was crystallised from dilute alcohol, m.p. 72°. (Found: C, 41.01; H, 3.85; I, 33.58. $C_{13}H_{15}O_5$ I requires C, 41.27; H, 3.97; I, 33.39%.)

2-Acetyl-6-iodo-5-methoxyphenoxyacetic acid: The above ester (1 g.) was mixed with alcoholic sodium hydroxide solution (20 ml., 10%) and stirred for 10 min. at room temperature. The product which separated on acidification, crystallised from water, m.p. 143°. (Found C, 37.56; H, 3.08; I, 36.13. $C_{11}H_{11}O_5I$ requires C, 37.71; H, 3.14; I, 36.28%).

The above acid (1 g.) was refluxed with acetic anhydride (8 ml.) and fused sodium acetate (2.5 g.) for 1 hr. on a sand bath and the reaction mixture worked up as usual. The product crystallised from dilute alcohol, m.p. 99°. Mixed m.p. with 7-iodo-6-methoxy-3-methylbenzofuran described above was not depressed.

Iodination of methyl 6-methoxy-3-methyl coumarilate with iodine in the presence of iodic acid: Methyl 6-methoxy-3-methyl-coumarilate (0.6 g.) in alcohol (10 ml.) was treated with iodine (0.3 g.) and iodic acid (0.2 g.) The reaction mixture was stirred for 4 hr. The separated product was refluxed with alcohol and filtered. The filtrate on cooling gave a product which was recrystallised from alcohol, m.p. 160°. Mixed m.p. with an authentic sample of methyl 5-iodo-6-methoxy-3-methylcoumarilate³ was not depressed. The product which remained insoluble in hot alcohol was crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 180°. Mixed m.p. with an authentic specimen of methyl 7-iodo-6-methoxy-3-methylcoumarilate³ was not depressed.

Iodination with large excess (16 equivalents) of iodine and iodic acid gave the same mixture of 5-and 7-iodo derivatives in better yield.

Ethyl-2-acetyl-6-bromo-3-methoxyphenoxyacetate: 2-Hydroxy-3-bromo-6-methoxyacetophenone (1.2 g.) was refluxed with ethyl bromoacetate (0.83 g.) in the presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate (2 g.) in acetone (50 ml.) for 6 hr. Acetone was removed and the reaction mixture was added to water. The expected ester separated in liquid form (1 g.).

2-Acetyl-6-bromo-3-methoxyphenoxyacetic acid: The above oily ester (1 g.) was heated with alcoholic sodium hydroxide solution (20 ml.; 10%) on a steam bath for 2 hr. The product which separated on acidification crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether mixture, m.p. 117°. (Found: C, 43.18; H, 3.43; Br, 26.52. $C_{11}H_{11}O_5Br$ requires C, 43.57; H, 3.63; Br, 26.46%).

7-Bromo-4-methoxy-3-methylbenzofuran: The above acid (1 g.) was refluxed with acetic anhydride (6 ml.) and fused sodium acetate (2.5 g.) for 90 min. on a sand bath. The reaction mixture was poured in water and the product which separated crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 69°; yield 0.49. (Found: C, 49.86; H, 3.66; Br, 33.01. $C_{10}H_9O_2Br$ requires C, 49.79; H, 3.74; Br, 33.20%).

Ethyl 2-acetyl-4-iodo-3-methoxyphenoxyacetate: 2-Hydroxy-5-iodo-6-methoxyacetophenone (0.97 g.) was refluxed with ethyl bromoacetate (0.55 g.) in the presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate (2 g.) in acetone (30 ml.) on a steam bath for 6 hr. The acetone was removed and the reaction mixture was added to water. The expected ester separated in liquid form (0.8 g.)

2-Acetyl-4-iodo-3-methoxyphenoxyacetic acid: The above ester (1 g.) was stirred with alcoholic sodium hydroxide solution (20 ml.; 10%) at room temperature for 4 hr. The product which separated on acidification crystallised from benzene, m.p. 120°; yield 0.7 g. (Found: C, 37.33; H, 2.99; I, 36.47. $C_{11}H_{11}O_5I$ requires C, 37.71; H, 3.43; I, 36.28%).

5-Iodo-4-methoxy-3-methylbenzofuran: 2-Acetyl-4-iodo-3-methoxy-phenoxyacetic acid (1 g.) was refluxed with acetic anhydride (6 ml.) and fused sodium acetate (2.5 g.) for 4 hr. on a sand bath. The reaction mixture was added to water and the product which separated crystallised from dilute acetic acid, m.p. 76°; yield 0.4 g. (Found: C, 41.22; H, 3.00; I, 44.34. $C_{10}H_9O_2I$ requires C, 41.58; H, 3.13; I, 44.16%).

Ethyl 2-formyl-4-bromo-6-methoxyphenoxyacetate: 5-Bromo-2-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzaldehyde (1 g.) was refluxed with ethyl bromoacetate (0.8 g.) in the presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate (2 g.) in acetone (50 ml.) on a steam bath for 6 hr. Acetone was removed and the reaction mixture was added to water and the product which separated crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 101°; yield 1 g. (Found: C, 45.11; H, 3.91; Br, 25.70. $C_{12}H_{13}O_5Br$ requires C, 45.42; H, 4.10; Br, 25.23%).

2-Formyl-4-bromo-6-methoxyphenoxyacetic acid: Ethyl 2-formyl-4-bromo-6-methoxyphenoxyacetate (1 g.) was stirred with alcoholic sodium hydroxide solution (20 ml., 10%) for 30 min. at room temperature. The resulting solution was acidified and the separated product crystallised from water, m.p. 146°; yield 0.7 g. (Found: C, 41.15; H, 2.90; Br, 27.28. $C_{10}H_9O_5Br$ requires C, 41.53; H, 3.11; Br, 27.68%).

5-Bromo-7-methoxycoumarilic acid: 2-Formyl-4-bromo-6-methoxy-phenoxyacetic acid (1 g.) was refluxed with acetic anhydride (6 ml.) and freshly fused sodium acetate (2.5 g.) for 90 min. on a sand bath. The reaction mixture was added to water and the product which separated crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 250°; yield 0.5 g. (Found: C, 44.00; H, 2.20; Br, 29.93. $C_{11}H_9O_4Br$ requires C, 44.28; H, 2.58; Br, 29.52%).

The above acid was also prepared as follows:

5-Bromo-2-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzaldehyde (2.3 g.) was refluxed with ethyl bromomalonate (2.4 g.) in the presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate (5 g.) in ethyl methyl ketone (50 ml.) for 6 hr. on a steam bath. The solvent was removed and the reaction mixture was added to water. The product separated in a liquid form (1.1 g.). This oily ester (1 g.) was heated with alcoholic potassium hydroxide solution (20 ml.; 10%) on a steam bath for 1 hr. The product which separated on acidification was crystallised from alcohol. M.P. and mixed m.p. with 5-bromo-7-methoxycoumarilic acid was 250°. Decarboxylation of this acid (0.5 g.) by refluxing with copper (0.1 g.) and quinoline (2 ml.) gave an oil which could not be purified as the quantity was very small.

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